

On Weakly Berwald Finsler Special (α, β) –metric

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Abstract: In this paper, we study the special (α, β) -metric $F = \frac{\alpha^2}{\alpha - \beta} + \beta$ on a manifold M . Then prove that F is of scalar flag curvature and isotropic S -Curvature if and only if it is isotropic Berwald metric with almost isotropic flag curvature.

Key Words: Isotropic Berwald curvature; S -curvature; Weak berwald metric; almost isotropic flag curvature.

1. Introduction

Curvatures are the central concept of Finsler geometry. For a Finsler manifold (M, F) , the flag curvature is a function $K(P, y)$ to the tangent planes $P \subset T_x M$ and non zero $y \in P$. A Finsler metric F is of scalar flag curvature if for any non-zero vector $y \in T_x M$, $K = K(x, y)$ is of independent P containing $y \in T_x M$ (hence $K = \sigma(x)$ when F is Riemannian) It is of almost isotropic flag curvature if

$$K = \frac{3c_x y^m}{F} + \sigma, \quad (1.1)$$

where $c = c(x)$ and $\sigma = \sigma(x)$ are scalar functions on M . It is one of the important problems in Finsler geometry is to study and characterize Finsler manifolds of almost isotropic flag curvature [11].

To study the geometric properties of a Finsler metric, one also considers non-Riemannian quantities. In Finsler geometry, there are several important non-Riemannian quantities: the Cartan torsion C , the Berwald curvature B , the mean Landsberg curvature J and S -curvature S , etc ([6] [9] [13] [20]). these are geometric quantities which vanish for Riemannian metrics.

Among the non-Riemannian quantities, the S -curvature $S = S(x, y)$ is closely related to the flag curvature which constructed by Z . Shen for given comparison theorems on Finsler manifolds. An n -dimensional Finsler metric F is said to have isotropic S -curvature if

$$S = (n + 1)cF, \quad (1.2)$$

for some scalar function $c = c(x)$ on M . In [13], it is proved that if a Finsler metric F of scalar flag curvature is of isotropic S -curvature (1.2), then it has almost isotropic flag curvature (1.1).

The geodesic curves of a Finsler metric $F = F(x, y)$ on a smooth manifold M , are determined by $\ddot{c}^i + 2G^i(\ddot{c}) = 0$, where the local functions $G^i = G^i(x, y)$ are called the spray coefficients. A Finsler metric F is called a Berwald metric, if G^i are quadratic in $y \in T_x M$ for any $x \in M$.

A Finsler metric F is said to be isotropic Berwald metric if its Berwald curvature is in the following form

$$B_{jkl}^i = c\{F_{y^j y^k} \delta_j^i + F_{y^k y^l} \delta_l^i + F_{y^l y^j} \delta_k^i + F_{y^j y^k y^l y^i}\}, \quad (1.3)$$

where $c = c(x)$ is a scalar function on M [6].

As a generalization of Berwald curvature, Basco-Matsumoto proposed the notion of Douglas curvature [1]. A Finsler metric is called a Douglas metric if $G^i = \frac{1}{2} \Gamma_{jk}^i(x) y^j y^k + P(x, y) y^i$. In order to find explicit examples of Douglas metrics, i.e we considered some (α, β) -metrics. An (α, β) -metric is a Finsler metric of the form $F = \alpha \varphi\left(\frac{\beta}{\alpha}\right)$, where $\varphi = \varphi(s)$ is a C^∞ on $(-b_0, b_0)$ with certain regularity, $\alpha = \sqrt{a_{ij}(x) y^i y^j}$ is a Riemannian metric and $\beta = b_i(x) y^i$ is a 1-form on M .

In this paper, we consider special metric $F = \frac{\alpha^2}{\alpha - \beta} + \beta$ with some non-Riemannian curvature properties and prove the following.

Theorem 1.1. Let $F = \frac{\alpha^2}{\alpha - \beta} + \beta$ be a non-Riemannian special metric on a manifold M of dimension n . Then F is of scalar flag curvature with isotropic S-curvature (1.2), if and only if it has isotropic Berwald curvature (1.3) with almost isotropic flag curvature (1.1). In this case, F must be locally Minkowskian.

2. Preliminaries

Let M be an n -dimensional C^∞ manifold. Denote by $T_x M$ the tangent space at $x \in M$, by $TM = \cup_{x \in M} T_x M$ the tangent bundle of M and by $TM_0 = TM \setminus \{0\}$ the slit tangent bundle on M is a function $F : TM \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ which has the following properties:

- F is C^∞ on $TM \setminus \{0\}$;
- F is positively 1-homogeneous on the fibers of tangent bundle TM ;
- For each $y \in T_x M$, the following quadratic form g_y on $T_x M$

$$g_y(u, v) := \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial s \partial t} [F^2(y + su + tv)]|_{s=t=0}, u, v \in T_x M.$$

Let $x \in M$ and $F_x := F|_{T_x M}$. To measure the non-Euclidean feature of F_x , define $C_y : T_x M \otimes T_x M \otimes T_x M \rightarrow R$ by

$$C_y(u, v, w) := \frac{1}{2} \frac{d}{dt} [g_y + tw(u, v)]|_{t=0}, u, v, w \in T_x M.$$

The family $C := \{C_y\}_{y \in TM_0}$ is called the cartan torsion. It is well known that $C = 0$ if and only if F is Riemannian [17]. For $y \in T_x M_0$, mean cartan torsion I_y by $I_y(u) := I_i(y) u^i$, where $I_i := g^{jk} C_{ijk}$, By Diecke theorem, F is Riemannian if and only if $I_y = 0$.

The horizontal covariant derivatives of I along geodesics give rise to the mean Landsberg curvature $J_y(u) := J_i(y) u^i$, where $J_i := I_i|_s y^s$. A Finsler metric is said to be weakly Landsbergian if $J = 0$.

Given a Finsler manifold (M, F) , then a global vector field G is induced by F on TM_0 , which in a standard coordinate (x_i, y_i) for TM_0 is given by $G = y^i \frac{\partial}{\partial x^i} - 2G^i(x, y) \frac{\partial}{\partial y^i}$, where

$$G^i := g^{il} \left[\frac{\partial^2(F^2)}{\partial x^k \partial y^l} y^k - \frac{\partial(F^2)}{\partial x^l} \right], y \in T_x M.$$

Let G is called the spray associated to (M, F) . In local coordinates, a curve $c(t)$ is geodesic if and only if its coordinates $c^i(t)$ satisfy $\ddot{c}^i + 2G^i(\dot{c}) = 0$,

For a tangent vector $y \in T_x M_0$, define $B_y : T_x M \otimes T_x M \otimes T_x M \rightarrow T_x M$ and $E_y : T_x M \otimes T_x M \rightarrow R$ by

$$B_y(u, v, w) := B_{jkl}^i(y) u^j v^k w^l \frac{\partial}{\partial x^i} \Big|_x \text{ and } E_y(u, v) := E_{jk}(y) u^j v^k, \text{ where}$$

$$B_{jkl}^i = \frac{\partial^3 G^i}{\partial y^j \partial y^k \partial y^l}, \quad E_{jk} = \frac{1}{2} B_{ijm}^m.$$

Let B and E are called the Berwald curvature and mean Berwald curvature, respectively. Then F is called a Berwald metric and weakly Berwald metric if $B = 0$ and $E = 0$, respectively.

A Finsler metric F is said to be isotropic mean Berwald metric if its mean Berwald curvature is in the following form

$$E_{ij} = \frac{n+1}{2F} c h_{ij},$$

where $c = c(x)$ is a scalar function on M and h_{ij} is the angular metric [6].

Define $D_y: T_x M \otimes T_x M \otimes T_x M \rightarrow T_x M$ by $D_y(u, v, w) := D_{jkl}^i(y) u^i v^j w^k \frac{\partial}{\partial x^i} |_x$ where

$$D_{jkl}^i := B_{jkl}^i - \frac{2}{n+1} \{E_{jk} \delta_l^i + E_{jl} \delta_k^i + E_{kl} \delta_j^i + E_{jk} l y^i\}.$$

We call $D := \{D_y := \{D_{jkl}^i\}_{y \in TM_0}\}$ the Douglas curvature. A Finsler metric with $D = 0$ is called a Douglas metric. The notion of Douglas metrics was proposed by Basco-Matsumoto as a generalization of Berwald metrics [1]. For a Finsler metric F on an n-dimensional manifold M, the Busemann-Hausdorff volume form $dV_F = \sigma_F(x) dx^1 \dots dx^n$ is defined by

$$\sigma_F(x) = \frac{Vol(B^n(1))}{Vol\{(y^i) \in R^n | F(x, y) < 1\}}$$

In general, the local scalar function $\sigma_F(x)$ can not be expressed in terms of elementary functions, even F is locally expressed by elementary functions. Let G^i denote the geodisc coefficients of F in the same local coordinate system. The S-curvature can be defined by

$$S(Y) := \frac{\partial G^i}{\partial y^i}(x, y) - y^i \frac{\partial}{\partial x^i} [ln \sigma_F(x)],$$

where $Y = y^i \frac{\partial}{\partial x^i} |_x \in T_x M$. It is proved that $S = 0$ if F is a Berwald metric. There are many non-Berwald metrics satisfying $S = 0$. S said to be isotropic, if there is a scalar functions $c(x)$ on M such that $S = (n+1)c(x)F$.

The Riemann curvature $R_y = R_k^i dx^k \otimes \partial x^i |_x: T_x M \rightarrow T_x M$ is a family of linear maps on tangent spaces, defined by

$$R_k^i = \frac{2\partial G^i}{\partial x^k} - \frac{\partial^2 G^i}{\partial x^j \partial y^k} y^j + 2G^i \frac{\partial^2 G^i}{\partial y^j \partial y^k} - \frac{\partial G^i}{\partial y^j} \frac{\partial G^j}{\partial y^k}.$$

For a flag $P = span\{y, u\} \subset T_x M$ with flagpole y, the flag curvature $K = K(p, y)$ is defined by

$$K(P, y) := \frac{g_y(u, R_y(u))}{g_y(y, y)g_y(u, u) - g_y(y, u)^2}.$$

We say that a Finsler metric F is of scalar curvature if for any $y \in T_x M$, the flag curvature $K = K(x, y)$ is a scalar function on the slit tangent bundle TM_0 . In this case, for some scalar function K on TM_0 the Riemann curvature is in the following form

$$R_k^i = KF^2 \{\delta_k^i - F^{-1} F_{,k} y^i\}.$$

If $K = \text{constant}$, then F is said to be of constant flag curvature. A Finsler metric F is called isotropic flag curvature, if $K = K(x)$.

3. Proof of theorem 1.1

Let $F = \alpha \varphi(s), s = \frac{\beta}{\alpha}$ be an (α, β) -metric, where $\varphi = \varphi(s)$ is a C^∞ on $(-b_0, b_0)$ with certain regularity,

$\alpha = \sqrt{a_{ij}(x) y^i y^j}$ is a Riemannian metric and $\beta = b_i(x) y^i$ is a 1-form on a manifold M. Let

$$r_{ij} = \frac{1}{2}(b_{i|j} + b_{j|i}), \quad s_{ij} = \frac{1}{2}(b_{i|j} - b_{j|i}),$$

$$s_j = b^i s_{ij}, \quad r_j = b^i r_{ij}.$$

where $b_{i|j}$ denote the coefficients of the covariant derivative of β with respect to α . Let

$$r_{i0} := r_{ij} y^j, \quad s_{i0} := s_{ij} y^j, \quad r_0 := r_j y^j, \quad s_0 := s_j y^j.$$

Put

$$Q = \frac{\varphi'}{\varphi - s\varphi'}, \quad \Theta = \frac{(\varphi - s\varphi')'''' - s\varphi\varphi''}{2\varphi((\varphi - s\varphi') + (b^2 - s^2)\varphi'')}, \quad \Psi = \frac{\varphi''}{2((\varphi - s\varphi') + (b^2 - s^2)\varphi'')}.$$

Then the S-curvature is given by

$$S = [Q' - 2\Psi Q_s - 2(\Psi Q)'(b^2 - s^2) - 2(n+1)Q\Theta + 2\lambda]s_0$$

$$+ 2(\Psi + \lambda)r_0 + \alpha^{-1}[(b^2 - s^2)\Psi' + (n+1)\Theta]r_{00}. \quad (3.2)$$

Let us put

$$\Delta = 1 + sQ + (b^2 - s^2)Q'$$

$$\Phi = -\{n\Delta + 1 + sQ\}(Q - sQ') - (b^2 - s^2)(1 + sQ)Q'',$$

In [5], Cheng- Shen characterize (α, β) –metrics with isotropic S –curvature.

Lemma 3.1. ([5]) Let $F = \alpha\varphi(\frac{\beta}{\alpha})$ be an (α, β) -metric on an n-manifold. Then, F is of isotropic S -curvature $S = (n + 1)cF$, if and only if one of the following holds

(i) β satisfies

$$r_{ij} = \epsilon\{b^2 a_{ij} - b_i b_j\}, \quad s_j = 0, \quad (3.3)$$

Where $\epsilon = \epsilon(x)$ is a scalar function and $\varphi = \varphi(s)$ satisfies

$$\Phi = -2(n+1)k \frac{\varphi\Delta^2}{b^2 - s^2},$$

where k is a constant. In this case, $c = k\epsilon$.

(i) β satisfies

$$r_{ij} = 0, \quad s_j = 0. \quad (3.4)$$

In this case, $c = 0$.

Let

$$\Psi_1 = \sqrt{b^2 - s^2 \Delta^{\frac{1}{2}} \left[\frac{\sqrt{b^2 - s^2}}{\Delta^{\frac{3}{2}}} \Phi \right]'},$$

$$\Psi_2 = 2(n+1)(Q - sQ') + 3 \frac{\Phi}{\Delta}.$$

$$\theta := \frac{Q - sQ'}{2\Delta}. \quad (3.6)$$

Then the formula for the mean Cartan torsion of an (α, β) –metric is given by following

$$I_i = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial}{\partial y^i} \left[\frac{(n+1)\varphi'}{\varphi} - \frac{(n-2)s\varphi''}{\varphi - s\varphi'} - \frac{3s\varphi'' - (b^2 - s^2)\varphi'''}{\varphi - s\varphi' + (b^2 - s^2)\varphi''} \right]$$

$$I_i = -\frac{\Phi(\varphi - s\varphi')}{2\Delta\varphi\alpha^2} (\alpha b_i - sy_i). \quad (3.7)$$

In [7], it is proved that the condition $\Phi = 0$ characterizes the Riemannian metrics among (α, β) -metrics. Hence, in the continue, we suppose that $\Phi \neq 0$.

Let $G^i = G^i(x, y)$ and $\bar{G}_\alpha^i = \bar{G}_\alpha^i(x, y)$ denote the coefficients of F and α respectively in the same coordinate system. By definition, we have

$$G^i = \bar{G}_\alpha^i + Py^i + Q^i,$$

where

$$P := \alpha^{-1}\Theta[-2Q\alpha s_0 + r_{00}]$$

$$Q^i := \alpha Qs_0^i + \Psi[-2Q\alpha s_0 + r_{00}]\mathbf{b}^i.$$

Simplifying (3.8) yields the following

$$G^i = \bar{G}_\alpha^i + \alpha Qs_0^i + \Theta\{-2\alpha Qs_0 + r_{00}\} \left\{ \frac{y^i}{\alpha} + \frac{Q'}{Q-sQ} \mathbf{b}^i \right\}, \quad (3.9)$$

Clearly, if β is parallel with respect to α ($r_{ij} = 0$ and $s_{ij} = 0$), then $P = 0$ and $Q^i = 0$. In this case, $G^i = \bar{G}_\alpha^i$ are quadratic in y , and F is a Berwald metric.

For an (α, β) -metric $F = \alpha\varphi(s)$, the mean Landsberg curvature is given by

$$J_i = -\frac{1}{2\Delta\alpha^4} \left\{ \frac{2\alpha^2}{b^2 - s^2} \left[\frac{\Phi}{\Delta} + (n+1)(Q - sQ') \right] (s_0 + r_0) h_i \right.$$

$$+ \frac{\alpha}{b^2 - s^2} \left[\Psi_1 + s \frac{\Phi}{\Delta} \right] (r_{00} - 2Q\alpha s_0) h_i + \alpha [-\alpha Q' s_0 h_i$$

$$+ \alpha Q(\alpha^2 s_i - y_i s_0) + \alpha^2 \Delta s_{i0}] + [\alpha^2 (r_{i0} - 2\alpha Q s_i) - r_{00} - 2\alpha Q s_0] y_i \frac{\Phi}{\Delta} \}. \quad (3.10)$$

Besides, they also obtained

$$\bar{J} = J_i b^i = -\frac{1}{2\Delta\alpha^2} \{ \Psi_1 (r_{00} - 2\alpha Q s_0) + \alpha \Psi_2 (r_0 + s_0) \}. \quad (3.11)$$

The horizontal covariant derivatives $J_{i;m}$ and $J_{i|m}$ of J_i with respect to F and α respectively are given by

$$J_{i;m} = \frac{\partial J_i}{\partial x^m} - J_l \Gamma_{im}^l - \frac{\partial J_i}{\partial y^l} N_m^l, J_{i|m} = \frac{\partial J_i}{\partial x^m} - J_l \bar{\Gamma}_{im}^l - \frac{\partial J_i}{\partial y^l} \bar{N}_m^l,$$

Where $\Gamma_{ij}^i = \frac{\partial G^l}{\partial y^i \partial y^j}$, $N_j^l = \frac{\partial G^l}{\partial y^j}$ and $\bar{\Gamma}_{ij}^l = \frac{\partial \bar{G}^l}{\partial y^i \partial y^j}$, $\bar{N}_j^l = \frac{\partial \bar{G}^l}{\partial y^j}$.

Then we have,

$$J_{i;m} y^m = \left\{ J_{i|m} - J_l (\Gamma_{im}^l - \bar{\Gamma}_{im}^l) - \frac{\partial J_i}{\partial y^l} (N_m^l - \bar{N}_m^l) \right\} y^m$$

$$= J_{i|m} y^m - J_l (N_i^l - \bar{N}_i^l) - 2 \frac{\partial J_i}{\partial y^l} (G^l - \bar{G}^l). \quad (3.12)$$

Let F be a Finsler metric of scalar flag curvature K . By Akbar-Zadeh's theorem it satisfies following

$$A_{ijk;s,m} y^s y^m + KF^2 A_{ijk} + \frac{F^2}{3} [h_{ij} K_k + h_{jk} K_j + h_{ki} K_i] = 0, \quad (3.13)$$

where $A_{ijk} = FC_{ijk}$ is the Cartan torsion and $K_i = \frac{\partial K}{\partial y^i}$ [2]. Contracting (3.13) with g^{ij} yields

$$J_{i;m} y^m + KF^2 I_i + \frac{n+1}{3} F^2 K_i = 0. \quad (3.14)$$

By (3.12) and (3.13), for an (α, β) -metric $F = \alpha\varphi(s)$ of constant flag curvature K , then

$$J_{i;m}y^m - J_l \frac{\partial(G^l - \bar{G}^l)}{\partial y^i} - \frac{2\partial J_l}{\partial y^l}(G^l - \bar{G}^l) + K\alpha^2\varphi^2 I_i = 0. \quad (3.15)$$

Contracting (3.15) with b^i implies that

$$\bar{J}_{|m} - J_i \alpha^{ik} b_{k|m} y^m - J_l \frac{\partial(G^l - \bar{G}^l)}{\partial y^i} b^i - \frac{2\partial J_l}{\partial y^l}(G^l - \bar{G}^l) + K\alpha^2\varphi^2 I_i b^i = 0. \quad (3.16)$$

There exists a relation between mean Berwald curvature E and the S -curvature S . Indeed, taking twice vertical covariant derivatives of the S -curvature gives rise the E -curvature. It is easy to see that, every Finsler metric of isotropic S -curvature (1.2) is of isotropic mean Berwald curvature (2.1). Now, is the equation $S = (n + 1cF$ equivalent to the equation $E = n + 12cF - 1h$?

Recently, Cheng-Shen prove that a Randers metric $F = \alpha + \beta$ is of isotropic S -curvature if and only if it is of isotropic E -curvature [4]. Then, Chun-Huan-Cheng [3] extend this equivalency to the Finsler metric $F = \alpha^{-m}(\alpha + \beta)^m + 1$ for every real constant m , including Randers metric .

To prove Theorem 1.1, we need the following.

Theorem 3.2. Let $F = \frac{\alpha^2}{\alpha - \beta} + \beta$ be a special metric on a manifold M of dimension n . Then the following are equivalent

- (i) F is of isotropic S -curvature, $S = (n + 1)c(x)F$;
- (ii) F is of isotropic mean Berwald curvature, $E = \frac{n+1}{2}cF^{-1}h$;

; where $c = c(x)$ is a scalar function on the manifold M .

In this case, $S = 0$. Then β is a Killing 1-form with constant length with respect to α , that is, $r_{00} = 0$.

Proof: (i) \rightarrow (ii) is obvious. Conversely, suppose that F has isotropic mean Berwald curvature, $E = \frac{n+1}{2}cF^{-1}h$. Then we have

$$S = (n + 1)[c(x)F + \eta], \quad (3.17)$$

where $\eta = \eta_i(x)y^i$ is a 1-form on M . For the special metric

$$Q = \frac{s^2+1}{s(s-2)}, \quad \Theta = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{s(s^3+3s-4)}{(s+s^2-1)(-s^3+2b^2)}, \quad \Psi = \frac{1}{-s^3+2b^2}. \quad (3.18)$$

By substituting (3.17) and (3.18) in (3.2), we have

$$\begin{aligned} S = & \left[-\frac{2(-3s^4 + 2sb^2 + 2s^3 - 2b^2 + 2s^2b^2 - 2s^2)}{s^2(s-2)^2(-s^3 + 2b^2)} + \frac{2(-3s^6 + 4s^5 + 4s^2b^2 - 5s^4 + 8s^3 + 4sb^2 - 4b^2)}{s^2(-s^3 + 2b^2)^2(s-2)^2} \right] \times \\ & (b^2 - s^2) - \frac{(n+1)(s^2+1)(-4+s^3+3s)}{(s-2)(-1+s+s^2)(-s^3+2b^2)} + 2\lambda \left[\frac{1}{-s^3+2b^2} + \lambda \right] r_0 \\ & - \left[\frac{3s^2(b^2 - s^2)}{\alpha(-s^3 + 2b^2)^2} \right] r_{00} - \left[\frac{(n+1)s(s^3 + 3s - 4)}{2\alpha(-1 + s + s^2)(-s^3 + 2b^2)} \right] r_{00}. \\ & (n+1) \left[c\alpha \left(1 + s + \frac{1}{s} \right) + \eta \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (3.19)$$

Multiplying (3.19) with $s(1 + s + s^2)(s^3 + 2b^2)^2(s + 2)\alpha^5$ implies that

$$M_1 + M_2\alpha^2 + M_3\alpha^4 + M_4\alpha^4 + M_5\alpha^8 + M_6\alpha^{10}[\alpha[M_7 + M_8\alpha^2 + M_9\alpha^4 + M_{10}\alpha^6 + M_{11}\alpha^8 + M_{12}\alpha^{10}]] = 0, \quad (3.20)$$

where

$$M_1 = \left[-\beta^2c(n+1) + 2\beta\lambda(s_0 + r_0) - \beta\eta(n+1) + \frac{r_{00}}{2}(n+1) \right] \beta^9,$$

$$M_2 = -\frac{1}{2} [10\beta^2 c(n+1) - 12\beta\lambda(s_0 + r_0) + 12\beta s_0 + 6\beta\eta(n+1) + 3r_{00}(n+3)]\beta^7,$$

$$M_3 = -[-5\beta^2 c(n+1) + 2\beta b^2 s_0(n+2) - 4\beta b^2 \eta(n+1) + 8\beta\lambda b^2(s_0 + r_0) + 2\beta(s_0(2n+3) + r_0) + r_{00}(2n-1)(b^2 + 2)]\beta^5,$$

$$M_4 = -2[-2\beta^2 b^4 c(n+1) - 2\beta b^4 \eta(n+1) + 4\beta b^4 \lambda(s_0 + r_0) - \beta((-ns_0 + 2r_0) + 3s_0) + 4\beta b^4 \lambda(s_0 + r_0) + 4\beta b^2 \eta(n+1) - 8\beta b^2 \lambda(s_0 + r_0) + 2\beta b^2((2n+3)s_0 + r_0) + r_{00}b^2(5n+8)]\beta^3,$$

$$M_5 = -2b^2[-4\beta c(n+1) + 10\beta b^2 c(n+1) - 12b^2 \lambda(s_0 + r_0) + 3(ns_0 - 2r_0) + 6b^2 \eta(n+1)]\beta^2,$$

$$M_6 = 20b^4 c(n+1)\beta,$$

$$M_7 = [2\beta\lambda(s_0 + r_0) + \beta s_0(n+1) - \beta\eta(n+1) + r_{00}(n+4)]\beta^8,$$

$$M_8 = [-4\beta^2 b^2 c(n+1) - 4\beta\lambda(s_0 + r_0) - 2\beta\eta(n+1) + 8\beta b^2 \lambda(s_0 + r_0) + 2\beta(r_0 - 2n(\eta b^2 + s_0)) + r_{00}n((b^2 + 5) - 2r_{00}(b^2 + 2))]\beta^6,$$

$$M_9 = [20\beta^2 b^2 c(n+1) - 2\beta^2 c(n+1) + 12\beta\eta b^2(n+1) - 24\beta b^2 \lambda(s_0 + r_0) + 3\beta(ns_0 + 2r_0) + 3\beta s_0(2b^2 - 3) + 3r_{00}b^2(4+n)]\beta^4,$$

$$M_{10} = 2b^2[-10\beta^2 c(n+1) - 2\beta\eta b^2(n+1) + 4\beta b^2 \lambda(s_0 + r_0) + \beta(4s_0 n + 2r_0 + 9s_0) + 4r_{00}(n+1)]\beta^2,$$

$$M_{11} = 8b^2[b^2 \eta(n+1) - 2b^2 \lambda(s_0 + r_0) - r_0 + ns_0]\beta,$$

$$M_{12} = -8b^4 c(n+1).$$

The term of (3.20) which is seemingly does not contain α^2 is M_1 . Since β^9 is not divisible by α^2 , then $c = 0$ which implies that

$$M_1 = M_7 = 0.$$

Therefore (3.20) reduces to following

$$M_2 + M_3\alpha^2 + M_4\alpha^4 + M_5\alpha^6 + M_6\alpha^8 = 0, \quad (3.21)$$

$$M_8 + M_9\alpha^2 + M_{10}\alpha^4 + M_{11}\alpha^6 + M_{12}\alpha^8 = 0. \quad (3.22)$$

By plugging $c = 0$ in M_2 and M_8 , the only equations that don't contain α^2 are the following

$$-\beta[2\lambda(s_0 + r_0) - (n+1)\eta + 3r_{00}(n+3)] = \tau_1\alpha^2, \quad (3.23)$$

$$4\beta b^2[2\lambda(s_0 + r_0) - (n+1)\eta] + r_{00}(2n-1)(b^2 + 2) = \tau_2\alpha^2, \quad (3.24)$$

where $\tau_1 = \tau_1\alpha^2$ and $\tau_2 = \tau_2\alpha^2$ are scalar functions on M. By eliminating $[2\lambda(s_0 + r_0) - (n+1)\eta]$, we get

$$r_{00} = \tau\alpha^2, \quad (3.25)$$

where $\tau = \frac{\tau_2 - 4b^2\tau_1}{(b^2+2)(4b^2(2n-1)) - 3(n+3)}$.

By (3.23) or (3.24), it follows that

$$2\lambda(s_0 + r_0) - (n+1)\eta = 0. \quad (3.26)$$

By (3.25), we have $r_0 = \tau\beta$. Putting (3.25) and (3.26) in M_8 and M_9 yields

$$M_8 = [n(b^2 + 5) - 2(b^2 + 2)]\tau\alpha^2\beta^6, \quad (3.27)$$

$$M_9 = [(6b^2 + 3n - 9)s_0 - 6r_0]\beta - 3b^2(n+4)r_{00}\tau\alpha^2\beta^4. \quad (3.28)$$

By putting (3.27) and (3.28) into (3.22), we have

$$[(6b^2 + 3n - 9)s_0 - 6r_0]\beta^5 - 3b^2(n+4)r_{00}\tau\alpha^2\beta^4 + n(b^2 + 5) - 2(b^2 + 2)\tau\alpha^2\beta^6$$

$$-M_{10}\alpha^2 + M_{11}\alpha^4 + M_{12}\alpha^6 = 0. \quad (3.29)$$

The only equations of (3.29) that do not contain α^2 is $[n(b^2 + 5) - 2(b^2 + 2)\tau\beta + (6b^2 + 3n - 9)s_0 - 6r_0]\beta^5$.

Since β^6 is not divisible by α^2 , then we have

$$[n(b^2 + 5) - 2(b^2 + 2)\tau\beta + (6b^2 + 3n - 9)s_0 - 6r_0] = 0. \quad (3.30)$$

By lemma 3.1, we always have $s_j = 0$. Then (3.30), reduces to following

$$[n(b^2 + 5) - 2(b^2 + 2)]\tau\beta - 6r_0 = 0. \quad (3.31)$$

Thus

$$[n(b^2 + 5) - 2(b^2 + 2)]\tau b_i - 6\tau b_i = 0. \quad (3.32)$$

By multiplying (3.32) with b^i , we have

$$\tau = 0.$$

Thus by (3.28), we get $\eta = 0$ and then $S = (n + 1)cF$. By (3.25), we get $r_{ij} = 0$. Therefore lemma 3.1, implies that $S = 0$. This completes the proof.

Proof of Theorem 1.1: Let F be an isotropic Berwald metric (1.3) with almost isotropic flag curvature (1.1). In [22], it is proved that every isotropic Berwald metric (1.3) has isotropic S -curvature (1.2).

Conversely, suppose that F is of isotropic S -curvature (1.2) with scalar flag curvature K . In [13], it is showed that every Finsler metric of isotropic S -curvature (1.2) has almost isotropic flag curvature (1.1). Now, we are going to prove that F is a isotropic Berwald metric. In [6], it is proved that F is an isotropic Berwald metric (1.3) if and only if it is a Douglas metric with isotropic mean Berwald curvature (2.1). On the other hand, every Finsler metric of isotropic S -curvature (1.2) has isotropic mean Berwald curvature (2.1). Thus for completing the proof, we must show that F is a Douglas metric. By proposition 3.2, we have $S = 0$. Therefore by theorem 1.1 in [13], F must be of isotropic flag curvature $K = \sigma(x)$. By proposition 3.2, β is a Killing 1-form with constant length with respect to α , that is, $r_{ij} = s_j = 0$. Then (3.9), (3.10) and (3.11) reduce to

$$G^i - \bar{G}^i = \alpha Q s_0^i, \quad J_i = -\frac{\Phi s_{i0}}{2\alpha\Delta}, \quad \bar{J} = 0.$$

By (3.8), we get

$$I_i b^i := -\frac{\Phi(\varphi - s\varphi')}{2\Delta F}(b^2 - s^2).$$

Now we consider two cases:

Case I: $\dim M \geq 3$. In this case, by Schur lemma F has constant flag curvature and (3.6) holds, the equation (3.16) reduces to following

$$\frac{\Phi s_{i0}}{2\Delta\alpha} \alpha^{ik} s_{k0} + \frac{\Phi s_{i0}}{2\Delta\alpha} (s Q s_0^i + Q' s_0^i (b^2 - s^2)) - KF \frac{\Phi}{2\Delta} (\varphi - s\varphi')(b^2 - s^2) = 0. \quad (3.33)$$

By assumption $\Phi \neq 0$. Thus by (3.32), we get

$$s_{i0} s_0^i + s_{i0} (\alpha Q s_0^i)_i b^i - KF \alpha (\varphi - s\varphi')(b^2 - s^2) = 0. \quad (3.34)$$

The following holds

$$(\alpha Q s_0^i)_i b^i = s Q s_0^i + Q' s_0^i (b^2 - s^2) = 0.$$

Then (3.34) can be rewritten as follows

$$s_{i0} s_0^i \Delta - K \alpha^2 \varphi (\varphi - s\varphi')(b^2 - s^2) = 0. \quad (3.35)$$

By (3.6), (3.18) and (3.35), we obtain

$$\left[1 + \frac{s^2+1}{s-2} - \frac{2(b^2-s^2)(-1+s+s^2)}{s^2(s-2)^2} \right] s_{i0} s_0^i - K \alpha^2 \left[\frac{(-1+s+s^2)(s-2)}{s^2} (b^2 - s^2) \right] = 0. \quad (3.36)$$

Multiplying (3.36) with $-s^2(s-2)^2\alpha^5$ yields

$$A + \alpha B = 0,$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} A &= -K20b^2\beta\alpha^6 + (5K\beta^3b^2 + 2b^2\beta s_{i_0}s_0^i + 20K\beta^3)\alpha^4 + (\beta^3s_{i_0}s_0^i - 5K\beta^5 + K\beta^5b^2)\alpha^2 \\ &\quad - K\beta^7 - s_{i_0}s_0^i\beta^5 \\ B &= 8Kb^2\alpha^6 + (10Kb^2\beta^2 - 8K\beta^2 - 2s_{i_0}s_0^ib^2)\alpha^4 + (-5Kb^2\beta^4 + 2s_{i_0}s_0^ib^2\beta^2 - 10K\beta^4)\alpha^2 \\ &\quad + (5K\beta^6 - s_{i_0}s_0^i\beta^4). \end{aligned}$$

Obviously, we have $A = 0$ and $B = 0$.

If $A = 0$ and the fact that β^7 is not divisible by α^2 , we get $K = 0$. Therefore (3.36) reduces to following

$$s_{i_0}s_0^i = a_{ij}s_0^js_0^i = 0.$$

Because of positive-definiteness of the Riemannian metric α , we have $s_{i_0} = 0$, i.e., β is closed. By $r_{00} = 0$ and $s_0 = 0$, it follows that β is parallel with respect to α . Then $F = \frac{\alpha^2}{\alpha-\beta} + \beta$ is a Berwald metric. Hence F must be locally Minkowskian.

Case II: Let $\dim M = 2$. Suppose that F has isotropic Berwald curvature (1.3). In [6], it is proved that every isotropic Berwald metric [3] has isotropic S -curvature, $S = (n + 1)cF$.

By proposition 3.2, $c = 0$. Then by [3], F reduces to a Berwald metric. Since F is non-Riemannian, then by Szabo's rigidity theorem for Berwald surface (see [2] page 278), F must be locally Minkowskian.

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